

Equilibrium constant,

$$E_{\text{Ti(Bo)}-\text{H}_2\text{Dp}}^{\text{org}} = \frac{[\text{Ti(HDp)}]_{\text{org}}[\text{HBo}]_{\text{org}}}{[\text{Ti(Bo)}]_{\text{org}}[\text{H}_2\text{Dp}]_{\text{org}}}$$

The chloroform solution of, thallium diphenylcarbazone on treatment with varying amounts of the chloroform solution of α -benzoin oxime, immediately liberates diphenylcarbazone. Equilibrium concentrations of all the species involved are determined as follows.

From the extinction coefficient of the complex, Ti(HDp) , equilibrium concentration of Ti(HDp) is found out. The difference between the absorbance before and after the equilibration corresponds to the change in concentration of Ti(HDp) and also may be used to measure the concentration of Ti(Bo) formed in the reaction. The equilibrium concentration of diphenylcarbazone liberated in the reaction is indirectly calculated and is taken same as that of the concentration of Ti(Bo) formed. Exactly the same amount, i.e. $[\text{Ti(Bo)}]$ or $[\text{H}_2\text{Dp}]$ is consumed in the reaction and, therefore, the equilibrium concentration of HBo is taken as $\{[\text{HBo}]_{\text{org}}\} - \{[\text{H}_2\text{Dp}]_{\text{formed}}\}$. The experimental conditions and the values of the equilibrium constants of the exchange reactions in chloroform are summarised in Table 1. The results reveal that the equilibrium constants can be determined accurately.

The work with diphenylcarbazone is likely to be less reliable and less reproducible partly because of the lack of characteristic differences in spectral properties of the diphenylcarbazones and due to the lack of report on structure and properties of these complexes.

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Kinetic Evidence for Steric Enhancement of Resonance in Vanadium(v) and Lead Tetraacetate Oxidation of Substituted Phenyl Methyl Sulphides†

P. V. V. SATYANARAYANA*, G. V. RAMANA
and

K. R. LAKSHMI

Department of Chemistry, Nagarjuna University,
Nagarjunanagar-522 510

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THE phenomenon of steric enhancement of resonance¹ received substantial evidence from the work carried out by various workers². As a part of the extension of the programme on oxidation of some substituted-phenyl methyl sulphides by vanadium(v) and lead tetraacetate, we obtained kinetic

evidence for the said phenomenon. We report here our results on oxidation of some substituted-phenyl methyl sulphides with vanadium(v) and lead tetraacetate.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Acetic acid was purified over chromium trioxide. The substituted-phenyl methyl sulphides were prepared by known procedures³. Double-distilled water was used for all the purposes. The reactions were followed by estimating the unreacted vanadium(v) and lead tetraacetate using the procedures given elsewhere⁴.

Results and Discussion

The second order rate constants for the oxidation of substituted-phenyl methyl sulphides by vanadium(v) in aqueous acetic acid are presented in Table 1. The oxidation is facilitated by electron-donating groups in the benzene ring and is retarded by the electron-withdrawing ones.

TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANTS FOR OXIDATION OF SOME SUBSTITUTED-PHENYL METHYL SULPHIDES BY VANADIUM(V)

Solvent = 50% aq. acetic acid, Temp. = 35°, $[\text{H}^+] = 0.1 \text{ M}$

Sulphide	k_a $\times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$		$k_{\text{obs}}/k_{\text{calc}}$
	Obs.	Calc.	
Methyl phenyl (1)	6.32	—	—
Methyl m-tolyl (2)	12.62	—	—
4-Methoxyphenyl methyl (3)	3 320.0	—	—
4-Methoxy-3-methylphenyl methyl (4)	16 400.0	6 629.5	2.47
3,5-Dimethylphenyl methyl (5)	25.39	25.20	1.01
3,5-Dimethyl-4-methoxyphenyl methyl (6)	426.0	19 238.0	0.032

p-Methoxyphenyl methyl sulphide (3) undergoes oxidation about 500-times faster than methyl phenyl sulphide (1) due to greater electron density at the sulphur atom caused by the resonance interaction of the methoxy group with the reaction centre. The observed rate constant for the oxidation of 4-methoxy-3-methylphenyl methyl sulphide (4) is significantly higher than the value predicted on the basis of the additivity of group effects indicating that there is greater conjugative interaction of methoxy group with the reaction centre in 4 than in 3. This enhancement of resonance is due to the steric effect of 3-methyl group (*ortho* to OCH_3) which restricts the free rotation of methoxy group thereby increasing the probability of the latter to attain planarity with the benzene ring.

It is also of interest to note that 3,5-dimethyl-4-methoxyphenyl methyl sulphide (6) undergoes oxidation at a slower rate than 3. In fact, the ratio $k_{\text{obs}}/k_{\text{calc}}$ in the case of 6 is far less than unity indicating that there is expected steric inhibition of resonance in 6. Also, the ratio of $k_{\text{obs}}/k_{\text{calc}}$ in 3,5-dimethylphenyl methyl sulphide (5) is almost unity indicating that the effect of groups is additive.

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The second order rate constant values for the oxidation of substituted-phenyl methyl sulphides by lead tetraacetate in acetic acid (Table 2) reveal that there is evidence for steric enhancement of resonance in 4. The expected evidence for the steric inhibition of resonance in 6 as well as additivity of group effects in 5 were also obtained.

TABLE 2—RATE CONSTANTS FOR OXIDATION OF SOME SUBSTITUTED-PHENYL METHYL SULPHIDES BY LEAD TETRAACETATE

Solvent=98% aq. acetic acid, Temp.=30°

Compd. no.	k_2 $\times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$		$k_{\text{obs}}/k_{\text{cat}}$
	Obs.	Calc.	
1	1.59	—	—
2	3.81	—	—
3	386.0	—	—
4	2540.0	924.9	2.75
5	9.00	9.12	0.99
6	154.0	2216.0	0.069

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Effect of Solvents of different Polarities on the Spectra of some Carboxyalkylthiocarbamides

P. S. MITTAL and NARINDER KUMAR

Department of Chemistry, D. N. College, Hisar-125 001

and

J. S. TYAGI

Meerut College, Meerut

and

A. D. TANEJA*

Department of Plant Breeding, Haryana Agricultural University, Hisar-125 004

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SOME work has been reported on thiocarbamides and substituted thiocarbamides with regards to their complexing ability, ionisation constants and fungicidal activity¹. The survey of the literature reveals that a little work has been reported on the spectral studies of carboxyalkylthiocarbamides. So it was thought desirable to study the effect of solvents of different polarities on electronic transition of carboxyalkylthiocarbamides.

The carboxyalkylthiocarbamides, viz *N*-methyl-(1), *N*-phenyl-(2) and *N*-allyl-*N*¹-(1,5-dicarboxy propyl)thiocarbamide(3), *N*-methyl-(4), *N*-phenyl-(5),

and *N*-allyl-*N*¹-(1,4-dicarboxyethyl)thiocarbamide(6); *N*-methyl-(7), *N*-phenyl-(8) and *N*-allyl-*N*¹-(carboxy ethyl)thiocarbamide(9), bis-*N*-methyl-(10), bis-*N*-phenyl-(11) and bis-*N*-allyl-*N*¹-(carboxyethylthio)thiocarbamide(12) were prepared as described earlier². Freshly distilled solvents³ were used in all the experiments and the solutions were prepared immediately before use. The absorbance measurements were made at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ with a PMQ-3, UV-VIS spectrophotometer using 1-cm matched quartz cells equipped with thermoplates to stabilise the temperature in a series of solvents varying in polarities from benzene (*Z*, 54.0) to ethylene glycol (*Z*, 85.1). The results are reported in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

It is evident from Table 1 that these carboxyalkylthiocarbamides exhibit three intense absorption maxima in the range 195–210, 235–255 and 260–300 nm, assigned to high energy $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ carboxyaryl, $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ thiocarbonyl and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ carboxyalkyl transitions, respectively^{4,5}. These bands exhibit a small shift in different solvents of varying polarities and is consistent with the expected spectrum of a molecule having an excited state which is more polar than the ground state. The transition energies of these carboxyalkylthiocarbamides were plotted against *Z*-values. The correlation between *Z* vs E_T gives a scatter diagram for which the best straight line was obtained by a least-square fit. In order to know the degree of relationship between the polarity of the solvent and the transition energy, a simple linear regression was fitted. The deviations in DMF, DMSO and FA are attributed to the charge transfer interaction between the solvent and carboxyalkylthiocarbamides. Since the molecules are bulky, it is difficult to achieve a fruitful relationship between *Z* and E_T because as the solute molecule increases in size, the correlation becomes less precise due to specific solute-solvent interactions, self-association and distortion of the cybotactic region⁶.

For the thiocarbonyl $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions, the plots of *Z* vs E_T were drawn, from which best straight line was obtained by a least-square fit. The deviation in case of AN may be due to the presence of polarised π bond in the solvent molecule which enables easy acceptance of electrons from sulphur of thiocarbonyl group resulting in the formation of complex⁶. The $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition appears to be mixed with some other transitions probably $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions of carbonyl group overlapping with it. The plots of *Z* vs E_T were drawn as explained earlier. High value of transition energy in AN (*Z*, 71.3) may be due to the presence of polarised π -bonds which enable easy acceptance of electrons from a complex. The solvent sensitivities measured as a difference in the excitations in ethylene glycol and benzene are presented in Table 2.

The difference in λ_{max} of the bands of compounds 1–3 is due to the greater electron-donating ability of propyl group in these carboxyalkylthio-